

Community Collaboration Mini-Grant Evaluation 18-month Follow Up Interview

INTRODUCTION

Thank you for taking the time to meet today. The purpose of this interview is to learn more about the longer-term impacts of your project since the conclusion of the grant period. This information will help us evaluate the C2G program and make any needed improvements. We want to hear from you about the project's progress and status, including any additional outcomes that have resulted since the grant period ended, the impact of your project on the communities you engaged, the utility of the C2G program in making this work possible, and your overall experience with the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center. This interview should take about 30-45 minutes.

First, can you tell us a little bit about your organization and your project?

PROJECT STATUS

First, we want to hear about the status of the project in the six months since the grant period ended.

1. How would you describe the status of your project? Is your project:
 - Active (still continuing the original activities);
 - Transitioned into a different project; or
 - Completed?

Probes:

- *If status is **active or transitioned**: Can you tell us a little bit more about how you have been able to sustain (or transition) your project activities?*
- *If status is **complete**: Can you describe why your project has ended? Are you looking for any opportunities to continue your projects activities?*
- *If the status of your project does not fit into any of the options above, how would you describe the status?*

PROJECT IMPACT

For this next series of questions, we are interested in hearing about your project accomplishments, and any new developments related to your work as a Community Collaboration Mini-Grant awardee.

2. Has your team had any additional accomplishments that have resulted from your participation in the Community Collaboration Mini Grant program?
Probe: Possible areas may include new external funding, publications or reports, increased testing services, developed educational materials, or community partnerships.
 - *If participant talks about education materials: Did you create educational materials, or did you utilize existing resources from another organization?*
3. Please describe any new project outcomes that have come out of your project since participating in the Community Collaboration Mini-Grant program?

Probes:

- *Provided training and education for community members around COVID-19 testing topics*

- *Provided funding to increase capacity for COVID-19 testing activities*
- *Generated COVID-19 testing communication materials*
- *Developed communities of practice with RADx-UP awardees*
- *Provided funding for community personnel training on COVID- 19 research*

If new results/outcomes are indicated: Tell us more about these new outcomes.

Probes: Were they unanticipated?

4. In addition to COVID-19 resources, did mini the grant help you to address any other resources in your community? For example, access to food, transportation, or other needed resources?
5. Can you tell us about any difficulties or challenges that you experienced carrying out your project in your community?

Probes:

- *Did you have any issues recruiting community members to participate?*
- *Accessing testing supplies?*
- *Did you have enough organizational members to carry out project, or other staffing issues?*

6. What lessons would you share with projects doing similar work to help with community engagement for COVID-19 testing?

Probe: Are there any lessons you would share about ensuring community inclusion in the project decision-making?

How did you make sure that community voices were included during the project period? (Some examples may include inviting community members to meetings, or having their representation on advisory boards or steering committees; getting feedback from community members on the project and incorporating that into your project activities (e.g. changing event times to reflect times that work best for communities))

7. What would you describe as the most significant change to result from your project in the communities you engaged?

Probes: Was this unintended? Probes that get participant to explain how and when did this change come about (in what contexts, etc).

COLLABORATIONS AND EXPERIENCE WITH CDCC

Finally, we are interested in hearing about your overall experience working with the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) as a Community Collaboration Mini-Grant awardee.

8. As you may know, your project was one of many other funded projects in the RADx-UP program. Please describe any collaborations your team has had with any other RADx-UP and/or C2G funded projects, during and/or since the grant period ended.

Probes:

- *What worked well working with other projects?*

- *If you didn't work with other projects, what would you have been helpful/needed to connect with those projects?*
- *How would you describe the type of collaboration? (e.g. ongoing, frequent, one-time, what role partners play, the development of the partnership etc.)*

9. Are you familiar with the NIH's CEAL- also known as the Community Engagement Alliance program? CEAL engages communities across the country with efforts focused on addressing the major impacts of COVID-19 on specific communities.

If yes – did your project have any collaborations with them?

If no – move to question 10.

Probes:

- *How would you describe the type of collaboration? (e.g. ongoing, frequent, one-time, what role partners play, the development of the partnership etc.)*
- *What worked well working with CEAL?*

10. What Coordination and Data Collection Center supports, if any, did your project use throughout the grant period?

Probes:

- *How frequent were these supports used?*
- *How would you describe the quality of the support you received from the CDCC throughout the grant period?*
- *If they did not use any CDCC supports: Why not?*

11. Please describe any resources or support from the Coordination and Data Collection Center that you have used since the grant period ended.

12. Do you have any feedback on how the Coordination and Data Collection Center can improve its support to projects?

Probe/ask follow up questions to better understand the experience with the CDCC. What events/interactions led to this feedback?

13. Lastly, is there anything else you'd like to share about your experience?

That concludes the Community Collaboration Mini-Grant 18-month follow up interview. Thank you for your time.